

IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION ON PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11498366>

Abstract. *The present article describes the positive impacts of international cooperation on professional activities of teachers in achieving excellent outcomes from the school students. The process of International cooperation/collaboration of teachers and the teacher exchange programs among different countries has proved to be the best way for the development of professional activities of teachers. The positive psychology and attitude of teachers will directly show positive impact on the students performance. The possible ways of making cooperation and collaboration with international standard organizations are discussed in detail.*

Keywords: *international cooperation, activities, attitude, collaboration.*

Introduction

Professional development in activities of teachers include such activities for which teachers improve their subject knowledge, effective skills, thoughts, attitudes and ethics by changing the practice of their traditional activities in the classroom, and thus improve the outcomes of the students (Zavašnik Arčnik et al. 2015, Sentočnik 2013). The effectiveness of black board system along with its pros and cons are discussed (Jamilah A. Aloklu) . The students of this generation are smart, fast learners, curious and active listeners. The use of ICT tools in every class room is becoming mandatory in every school (Orlando, 2015). Application oriented subjects in the curriculum design, sophisticated laboratory facility, well equipped library facility, online resources for downloading the books and information are becoming basic requirements in every school. The European Commission identified the need of highly structured and systematic modern educational technologies and invested considerable funding for implementation (Volante, 2016). The reports showed positive results and the outcomes are astonishing. The methods of professional development activities of the teachers through International cooperation requires a great financial support from national Government agencies and International funding agencies. Even with the provision of sophisticated laboratory facilities and science centers across the countries, there is a need of motivation for the students by the teachers. The basic point to consider regarding the school teacher is the upgradation. A teacher is a life long learner. As the technology is ever developing, the teacher should be updated in the subject knowledge and attitude according to the modifying curriculum. There are lot of unsolved problems and phenomenon in science (Johan Hansson 2022) and technology. The role of teacher is to figure out those unsolved questions and should be kept in front of the students. This is called research oriented teaching methodology which was proved to be the best way of teaching for students (Shabbir et al, 2019). In this context, developed countries are establishing small scale research laboratories in urban as well as rural schools and thereby providing practical/research oriented teaching methodology right from the school level

education. At the same time, in order to motivate the students towards learning through practice, the teacher should be updated in knowledge and technology. This is possible through so many ways out of which International cooperation is the best way and the details are discussed below.

International cooperation through teacher exchange program

International cooperation include all activities that are aimed to support people of a society/country who are in need of development/betterment in ever developing system of education. There are so many organizations and funding agencies for improving the quality of education such as banks and trusts in developed countries. Through international cooperation the teachers as well as students will be benefited through exchange of knowledge and culture. Especially in sciences, because of international cooperation, the teachers attitude and knowledge will be improved. Providing laboratory in each and every school in a country is practically difficult and hence through international cooperation, the teachers are able to gain sufficient practical knowledge through exchange programs. During past few decades, so many teacher exchange programs were conducted between India and US. Global Placements for (India, US, Maldives, Kirgistan and Africa), Place well consultancy for India and Africa etc., are few popular private consultancies in India are organizing these programs. Through international cooperation, there will be a standardization of curriculum with outcomes suitable for present industry requirement.

Methods of making International cooperation

- Government and Non-Government Agencies/Ministries
- Private Consultancies
- Direct Appointment with free lancers
- Through Research

Advantages/Impact of International cooperation on teacher efficiency

- A teacher will be self updated in his basic subject knowledge and turns into a high standard International teacher.
- Based on the standard model of education (as in developed countries) the teacher will design the curriculum according to the needs of the present industry through international cooperation.
- Earlier reports showed positive outcomes in the quality of teaching because of teacher exchange programs.
- The use of IT tools in every class room is common in well developed countries and hence the teachers in developing countries will improve/learn the use of IT tools in their home country.
- There are experts in some subjects while, in other typical subjects there may be inadequacy. Due to International cooperation, experts will be invited and hence the quality imbalance will be avoided.
- Frequent visits (or interaction through online) with subject experts in various fields will enhance the analyzing skills of teachers and hence they will act as a better guide to typical students. In simple words, the teacher becomes an International teacher and guides the student in the best way.
- The teacher's practical knowledge/practical oriented teaching methodology will be improved which is mandatory for the future generation students.
- Research oriented teaching methodology is possible through International cooperation as research needs International collaboration.

● Without investing more budget on sophisticated laboratories and libraries, by the use of online resources (softwares), international cooperation provides much advanced and sophisticated quality education to the students through teachers.

Conclusion

The activities of teacher in the class room plays an important role in providing quality education to the new generation students. The students being smart and fast learners, according to the needs of Industry, the teacher should enhance himself/herself in latest teaching skills that gives a positive outcome from the student. To some extent it is difficult for any Government to provide all the updated facilities along with quality education in all subjects in every school and hence there is a need of International cooperation. There are so many advantages of International cooperation through which the activities of a teacher can be improved. The use of IT tools in the class rooms to research oriented teaching methodology requires International cooperation. There are few Global funding agencies that are providing special funds in improving the quality of education in under-developed countries. Few examples of teacher exchange programs between developed and developing countries are also discussed in this article. The impact of activities of teachers and the positive outcomes from the students are discussed in brief.

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